

Research Project Report:

Understanding the community value from implementing
the Food for Thought programme in Doncaster:

Learning and perspectives from key stakeholders and
parents

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Acknowledgements

The authors would like to express their gratitude to all the participants in the research who offered their time and insights to this research project

Funding support

This project was supported by Remake Learning's Moonshot Grants, an initiative that invests in bold, future-focused educational ideas. More information about this grant is accessed here:
<https://remakelearning.org/our-network/special-projects/moonshot-grants/>

Moonshot Grants are generously funded by The Grable Foundation, Richard King Mellon Foundation, The William and Flora Hewlett Foundation, Siegel Family Endowment, and The Heinz Endowments.

We gratefully acknowledge their support.

Part of the grant was used to commit to this research project.

1. Executive Summary

1.1. Background

The Food for Thought programme aimed to promote healthy eating, cultural exchange, and practical food skills by embedding experiential learning opportunities within two primary schools which serve highly multicultural communities in Doncaster. The programme sought to create inclusive spaces for families to connect, share traditions, and influence food provision within the school environment using cooking and growing workshops.

1.2. Research project aims and research questions

The main aim of this research was to understand the community value from implementing the Food for Thought programme in Doncaster and explore the learning and perspectives from key stakeholders and parents that were involved. This would be considered as a separate piece of evaluative work which was conducted alongside an operational team for this programme. In this research we explored the following research questions:

- How was the programme planned, delivered, and received?
- Why did community members attend and how did they contribute?
- How did the programme influence school food provision and learning environments?

1.3. Methods

A qualitative design was adopted using three semi-structured focus groups with 28 participants (stakeholders and parents) across two schools and the local council. Recruitment combined purposive and convenience sampling. Ethical approval was secured, and informed consent obtained. Data were transcribed, anonymised, and analysed using a deductive and inductive coding strategy, supported by inter-rater validation processes and checks.

1.4. Key Findings

Programme Planning and Delivery: The programme was praised for providing the **opportunity for skill development** from each other and its bold, adaptive design and this left participants **really wanting more**. **Differences on children's participation**, and **issues securing clear expectations** highlighted the need for clearer planning and improved consistency.

Programme Receipt: Parents reported **personal empowerment and achievement**, expressed **pride and enthusiasm of contribution**, and valued the **experiential learning opportunity** for themselves and their children.

Motivations for Attendance and Community Contribution: A range of factors, including **social connection**, **personal drivers**, **influencing personal positioning**, and **inclusivity creating involvement**, underpinned regular participation and supported cultural exchange and community bonding during the workshops.

Impact on Food Provision, Education and the Learning Environment: The **school acted as community hub around food**, and the programme supported **recognition of the food learning journey**, embedding practical skills and influencing attitudes toward healthy eating.

1.5. Summary

The Food for Thought programme demonstrated strong potential as an innovative, locally embedded approach for food education and social inclusion. While challenges in planning and delivery require attention, the overwhelmingly positive feedback, enjoyable and aspirational workshop content and clear demand for continuation emphasises the value of the programme. The research on the perspectives of participants does suggest that this can evolve into a sustainable initiative that enhances wellbeing, cultural exchange, and food education outcomes across Doncaster.

2. Introduction

2.1. Rapid Literature review

Schools provide continual access to children during a critical period of their development and are an ideal setting for health promotion (O'Brian et al., 2021; Pulimeno et al., 2020; WHO, 2017). Schools have long been regarded in the community as places for education and socialisation, offering a targeted physical, social and educational environment, making them key assets to guide health-promoting behaviours through policies and curricula (Caan et al., 2015; Galbraith et al., 2023; Sawyer et al., 2021). Effective strategies for promoting healthier eating among primary school children include providing opportunities for hands-on cooking and food growing (Chan et al., 2022; Vaughan, 2024), encouraging the uptake of nutritious school meals, and delivering comprehensive nutrition education (Garden et al., 2020; Haney et al., 2022).

Cooking classes lend themselves to community settings because they can be delivered in small groups and tailored to the needs of specific target populations (Garcia, 2020). In the United Kingdom (UK), the culture of home cooking has declined (Griffith, 2022). A reduction in home food preparation has been observed, with individuals from the lowest socio-economic groups displaying less confidence in food preparation (Adams et al., 2015). Previous systematic reviews have reported improvements in cooking confidence (Iacovou et al., 2013), diet quality, and cooking skills (Reicks et al., 2014), making cooking programmes a valuable intervention for enhancing food security and dietary habits among vulnerable populations.

Food growing is an important aspect of eating behaviours, with community gardens displaying improvements in health behaviours, increasing fruit and vegetable consumption and reducing sedentary behaviours (Egli et al., 2016; Kingsley et al., 2019; Wells et al., 2014). Furthermore, successes have been reported in knowledge translation, social connection and strengthening community connections across all age groups (Booth et al., 2018; Savoie-Roskos, 2017; Skelton, 2020). It is widely reported that interactions between people and nature have been shown to positively influence quality of life, including improving children's mood and wellbeing (Lampert et al., 2021; McCormick et al., 2017). Food growing within schools can foster autonomy, curiosity, and a renewed or enhanced interest in nature (Bergan et al., 2021; Chan et al., 2022). Consequently, school garden-based programmes are considered a promising and cost-effective way to improve children's knowledge, attitudes, and practices around healthy eating (Chan et al., 2022). These initiatives can also deepen children's understanding of food systems while encouraging healthier eating habits, a model that may be expanded to the local community to address system-level issues in food consumption (Davis, 2016).

Doncaster is currently confronted with significant socio-economic challenges, with over 45% of households experiencing or being at elevated risk of food insecurity (Department of Health and Social Care, 2022). Findings from the Doncaster 2025 Pupil Lifestyle Survey exhibit that approximately one-third of primary school-aged children do not consume fruit and vegetables daily (PFA Research, 2025). The borough also faces significant health inequalities, with some of the lowest healthy life expectancies in the country. Furthermore, stark disparities exist in overall life expectancy between the most deprived neighbourhoods. Although Doncaster's population is predominantly White English, Welsh, Scottish, Northern Irish or British, 13.4% of residents belong to other ethnic minority groups (Team Doncaster, 2022), highlighting the need for inclusive approaches. Doncaster has recently implemented a local Food Plan to address the key issues facing its residents with access to nutritious and affordable healthy food (Lamb, 2025). The FfT programme supports the objectives of that plan, facilitating cultural collaboration and healthy food behaviours in the City.

2.2. Rationale

Despite interest, there are few multi-component programmes which aim to address community-level challenges through the power of intergenerational, cross-cultural learning. As identified above, Doncaster has a multitude of pressing Public Health and socio-economic issues that may benefit from a school-based multi-component programme which provides both cooking and growing initiatives to local communities to address the challenges of poverty, healthy eating, community cohesion, and environmental sustainability. School-based multicomponent nutritional interventions are not without their complications and implementation effectiveness varies nationally (Chaudhary et al., 2020). Over the years, many articles highlight issues relating to design, description,

implementation, evaluation and sustainability (Middleton et al., 2012; Perera et al., 2015; Verdonschot et al., 2022). Interestingly, a review in the area has highlighted the necessity to address this gap in knowledge to better understand the impact of school-based projects on parents and families residing in local communities (Abderbwh et al., 2022). Evidence suggests that schools need to expand beyond their typical provision and serve as a hub for the community, where intergenerational and familial learning can take place (Cleveland et al., 2023; Trujillo-Torres et al., 2023).

Within the Doncaster local authority area, there are 19 different ethnicities (Office of National Statistics, 2023). It is recognised that cultural sharing through everyday practices significantly enhances social cohesion by providing platforms for diverse groups to interact, build trust, and develop a sense of belonging (Dadswell & Bungay, 2025; Wang et al., 2021). Food has long been a common connector within communities, with dietary beliefs and behaviours shaped during early childhood and passed down culturally across generations (Gregersen & Gillath, 2020). Food and food practices are surrounded by ritual and meaning. The practice of sharing food is a universal human tradition and facilitates cultural learning and community cohesion, and gaining respect for different cultures (Dunbar, 2017; Gatenby et al., 2011).

Within the United Kingdom (UK), there is an increased generational divide and fewer opportunities for meaningful intergenerational interaction (Miller & Abbott, 2025). Encouraging non-familial interaction between generations enhances mutual understanding and community cohesion (Campbell et al., 2023; Knight et al., 2014; Peters et al., 2021). There is a key opportunity for schools to become 'unwalled' and improve their relationship within the community, allowing them to be a central hub of the community, where shared learning can take place (Scherr et al., 2017).

2.3. Programme background and study aim

2.3.1. Background

Running between January 2025 and August 2025, Food for Thought (FFT) was developed and delivered via a multi-agency approach involving *Gro-box* (a Ltd company), City of Doncaster Council's Adult, Family, Community Learning (AFCL) team, two local primary schools in Doncaster and community members (parents of the local school children) taking part in the programme. The AFCL team received funding of £35729 from the 'Moonshot Grant' by *Remake Learning*, a leading peer-network for educators, researchers and innovators based in the United States. Remake Learning provide investment for ambitious projects and programmes which have the potential to transform education practices. This grant funding was secured based on the AFCL team delivering the aim of addressing the challenges of poverty, healthy eating, community cohesion, and environmental sustainability, by delivering a variety of practical learning experiences. These topics covered a wide range of ideas from food science, ecology, and sustainability to cooking methods, growing methods, culture, religion, and geography. With assistance from the local primary schools, the programme offered free-access spaces where parents could participate in learning activities together. The planned activities included (as objectives):

- 'Teach-ins' and 'skills swaps', enabling community members and unconventional educators to share and exchange expertise.
- Voluntary, Community and Faith-led intergenerational workshops, offering hands-on learning experiences that bring different age groups together.
- Outdoor learning to include allotment gardening, environmental experimentation, and nature-based skills.
- The development of practical resources, such as recipe collections and related guidance materials, to support continued learning beyond the sessions (Appendix A).
- Celebration events at each school, promoting the recipe collection and hosting a variety of wellbeing-based activities for families to get involved in.

To enable the FFT programme to attain these objectives, cooking and gardening workshops were established as the programme's core intervention components. Each school received 12 workshops, committing to one a month of both growing and cooking sessions. Descriptions and content of the workshops can be viewed in Appendix B. The programme was designed to challenge traditional notions of the school role and its relationship to the local

community by engaging 'unconventional educators' by recruiting parents. As a core part of the programme, parents had opportunities to share cultural cuisine, their experiences and traditions being active learners alongside their children, rather than passive participants. In total, there were 60 adults and children involved in growing workshops at the two school sites. There have been over 15 adults take part in the cooking workshops at each school site. To help facilitate and integrate the programme two members of staff were trained from each school.

Implementing school-based interventions and programmes effectively at a local level requires careful consideration of cultural relevance, resource availability, and community engagement to ensure sustainability and meaningful impact. Interestingly, few school-based nutritional interventions and / or programmes that involve community and parental involvement have been published in the research literature (Abderbwih et al., 2022; Scherr et al., 2017). To address this gap in knowledge, this research will play a critical role in understanding how the FfT programme's design, delivery and impact are perceived, enabling to identify best practices and inform future decision making.

2.3.2. School selection

The school sites selected for the FfT programme included two primary schools (Lakeside & Town Field), which serve multicultural communities. Notably, the Town Ward community includes a higher proportion of residents from an Asian background (11.9%) compared to the Doncaster average of 2.9%, further emphasising the need for culturally sensitive interventions (Office of National Statistics, 2023; Team Doncaster, 2022). Within this area, Town Field Primary School reports that their pupils speak various languages, with lots of children having English as an additional language. Both schools are close to high deprivation, where many families rely on emergency food parcels and face significant socio-economic challenges (UK Government, 2025). Internal council data suggest both free school meal uptake at Lakeside is 28% and 22% at Town Field with eligibility reported to be at 33.9% (Department of Education, 2025) and 31.5% (Department of Education, 2026) respectively.

2.3.3. Research aims and key questions

The main aim of this research was to understand the community value from implementing the Food for Thought programme in Doncaster and explore the learning and perspectives from key stakeholders and parents that were involved. We explored the following research questions:

- How was the FfT programme planned, delivered and received?
- Why did community members attend the FfT programme and how do they contribute?
- How did the FfT programme influenced school food provision, education and the environment for learning?

3. Research Methods

3.1. Design, recruitment and ethics

A qualitative research design used three focus groups (FGs) to gather data at two school locations within Doncaster (Lakeside & Town Field Primary Schools) and the City of Doncaster Council, Civic Building. FG 1 included primary stakeholders, consisting of Council Officers, School Staff and Voluntary Sector representatives. FG2 and 3 involved parents who attended the workshops. In total, 28 participants were recruited. Nine stakeholders attended FG 1, eleven in FG2 and eight in FG3. Characteristics and demographics of the participants can be viewed in Appendices C & D.

All FG participants were adult and non-vulnerable. Participants were recruited by a combination of word of mouth and personal invitation with the Children, Young People and Families directorate and the workshop delivery teams (both acting as a respective gatekeepers). Elements of both convenience (available and accessible) and purposive (participants must have experienced the FfT programme) sampling were used. This process was also supported by e-flyers, prospective participants being invited to contact the research team via email and / or call. Participants recruited into the study provided informed consent to the research team before their involvement and had the opportunity to ask questions after reading through an information sheet. Participants in FG 2 & 3 were offered a £25 gift voucher as a gesture of thanks for their time taking part.

FGs followed a semi-structured format, each recorded upon an encrypted handheld digital recorder. Participants were asked a series of questions and associated prompts according to a prepared guide (see Appendix E), which helped explore the main research questions in depth. By keeping the structure relatively open, a forum was provided for participants to discuss any issues that they viewed as important. Field notes were made alongside the audio recording. Ethical approval was granted for this research by Sheffield Hallam University (ER80251563).

3.2. Data Analysis

Audio files were listened to for familiarisation, transcribed verbatim and anonymised by the research team. The research team used both deductive and inductive processes at different stages of the analysis. An organisational framework allowed the authors to code for the specific research questions enabling a focused analysis on these aspects: i) Programme planning, delivery and receipt, ii) Motivations for attendance and Contribution and iii) Food provision, education and the environment for learning. A team of six researchers analysed the data performing interpretative (latent) coding throughout, to examine descriptions, conceptualisations, ideas and assumptions. Initially data was organised codebooks and progressed into themes. This was achieved via a consensus validation and inter-rater checking processes as part of the collaboration between research team members to confirm the final analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006; Fade & Swift, 2010; Harris et al., 2009).

4. Findings

The main findings are represented by the themes drawn from the coding framework. Main themes appear in **bold** (centred text) with related sub-themes presented in *italics* within the following text. In the following text, where quotes appear, the speaker is referenced as [Stakeholder type, FG number, participant number].

Collectively, Appendix F contains an overview of the qualitative analysis displaying all the findings for this project. The findings are discussed and then visualised under the next series of subheadings (4.1 to 4.4).

4.1. Programme Planning and Delivery

Stakeholders and parents provided valuable insight into the planning and delivery of the FfT Programme, identifying opportunities to maximise its learning potential. Parents with direct experienced of the programme expressed strong support for the content and the benefits this generated in the local community with many advocating for continuation. The programme was intentionally designed as a bold, ‘test and learn’ initiative, enabling innovation and adaptability in response to emerging needs. While this approach was widely regarded as a strength, feedback highlighted areas for improvement, including greater involvement of children in programme activities and the need for clear, consistent communication of expectations to parents. Improvable aspects on the challenges encountered with planning and delivery, include the involvement of the children in the programme and that clear and consistent communication on the expectations to parents would have been beneficial.

Opportunity for skill development from each other

This theme highlights the programme’s role in enabling parents from different cultural backgrounds to connect and then acquire skills through shared learning experiences. During the workshops there was *consideration of different*

ingredients and growing practices from different cultures and perspectives supplied by the parents:

"We've used everything that she fetched home and there was a lot of herbs and things and spices that I didn't know what there was, didn't know what there was for."

[Parent, FG3, P21]

"We describe everything to each other, you know, even spices, or, you know, ingredients, and, you know, the way of cooking, how you cook, how I cook, like that."

[Parent, FG3, P27]

The parental groups were able to have their own *exploration of culinary practices* and then try these in workshops with other parents facilitating and supporting skill development. There were frequent quotes outlining the involvement of parents in food preparation, cooking techniques and dish presentation. Additionally, a strong communal sentiment existed among parental groups, with clear satisfaction noted with the programme's components. The collaborative nature, whether through co-producing cuisine or growing food together, provided a real sense of *enjoyment taken from shared learning* as they experienced the programme collectively:

"So I think for me it was learning about other cultures, how they use spices, and then just learning how to roll a chapati properly, which was me. So things that I didn't know how, you know, Put it in your hand first and roll it."

[Parent, FG3, P25]

"Now everyone know how to make cooking."

[Parent, FG2, P14]

Really wanting more

This theme reflects the programme's ability to inspire ambition and engagement among participants, highlighting its potential to create meaningful learning experiences. There was a strong feeling of aspiration, coupled with frustration, with parents desiring greater access and engagement with the programme's components. Parents explained did explain that there were *unfinished food growing journeys* and *conflicting priorities* suggesting that the workshop provision and attendance may not have been sufficient for children to see the full potential of their planting efforts and the scheduled times and / or the duration of the workshops sometimes made attendance difficult:

"Just let the children, let them see what they grew, you know what I mean. Because he'd been waiting for carrot, but carrot didn't come till July"

[Parent, FG3, P22]

"I've missed a couple of the sessions due to circumstances needing to be at home."

[Parent, FG3, P21]

Additionally, parents did feel that a programme lack continuity and were disappointed due to the ending of the programme in their community. Parents looked forward to opportunities provided by the programme and there was a strong sense of *anticipation and demand for more workshops* to occur extending the programme in the local area:

"It's very good, I mean, was it a good thing?...All of them enjoyed my recipes and my ideas and my shortcuts and everything, so...So could you just do this again?"

[Parent, FG2, P11]

"I would have really liked to have done the cooking one. If it comes again, I would like to take part in that."

[Parent, FG3, P21]

Differences on children's participation

As this is a developmental project, parents offered a range of constructive ideas debating whether children should be involved in the practical cooking element of the programme. Parental opinions differed as to whether or to not involve the children in the practical cooking element of the programme. Some argued that *cooking without children facilitated social connection* and made it easier to make friends with other adults, and others suggested having children in the room whilst cooking would be adding complexity. Whilst others felt that there was a *missed opportunity for children* to be included, particularly related to parental time spent with children. Others argued that in future sessions and as the programme developed it would be preferable to involve children in this part of the programme:

"I think, personally, I think it would be really difficult to be...with children"

[Parent, FG2, P12]

"So I thought that would have been good for them as well, actually, because at home I don't even want them in the kitchen. I'm like...let me just finish cooking"

[Parent, FG2, P13]

Issues securing clear expectations

Participants sought some fine-tuning of processes to compliment their benefit from the programme and engagement with it, reflecting upon previous similar experiences. More initial clarity with regards *programme expectations*, particularly with respect to children participating within the cooking programme, would be beneficial. More prior notice of the type of cooking to be undertaken within the practical sessions would have also been appreciated. Stakeholders delivering the food growing sessions affirmed that the programme exceeded their expectations, due to high levels of participant engagement:

"I think we expected to go in and do what we normally do ... but I think we've seen a lot of interaction from the other parties...some of the results have been incredible"

[Stakeholder, FG1, P1]

"I didn't realise I was going to be cooking from scratch, but it is a good idea to"

[Parent, FG2, P13]

The majority of participants were *appreciative of difficulties in delivery* and acknowledged the complexities with running the project within school hours and using school facilities. Parents reflected on the need to be quiet during school hours, were appreciate of being able to utilise the school kitchen and the time constraints of both the school and the delivery staff.

"People can only commit so much, and the school can only commit so much time and resource to it."

[Parent, FG3, P25]

"And TEACHER NAME he came a couple of times, 'Be quiet, be quiet, quiet.'"

[Parent, FG3, P22]

Stakeholders reflected on the *recruitment techniques* utilised for the project and speculated how to secure wider engagement from the community, particularly from those parents that have not actively engaged within the school's outreach activities and wondered how other parents may be encouraged to get involved:

"I think that is possibly why some people have not engaged because they have no knowledge of any benefits, and they feel silly."

[Stakeholder, FG1, P8]

“We haven’t had that connection before. And so it was kind of new for us and so I just, I’m always on the gate every morning for parents anyway, but I literally had a conversations with lots of people and I think it did, well I know it did, bring some of those families in for sort of the first time if you like in a project like this. So it has to be you know that face to face kind of just come and try and see if you like it. It was that kind of conversation which worked to some extent.”

[Stakeholder, FG1, P2]

4.2. Programme Receipt

The focus groups highlighted a wide range of benefits associated with the programme, with participants expressing that the workshop sessions were fun and enjoyable. Stakeholders emphasised the programme’s role in raising awareness, building confidence to cook, grow, and prepare a variety of culturally diverse meals. Themes in this section address the programme’s influence on parents, including stories of personal empowerment, achievements, and how the cooking workshops allowed for opportunities to share their knowledge and skills with sense of pride and plenty of enthusiasm. Parents also reported developing new skills that reflected experiential learning.

Personal empowerment and achievement

This theme is illustrative of the powerful stories that emerged from the focus groups, with several parents discussing their achievements, and how knowledge gained from the workshops allowed for the *integration of learning into daily life* by taking ownership and influencing home life:

“Put it this way, I’ve got loads of plants growing in my garden! I’ve got seeds planted everywhere, so I don’t think what’s going to happen next year”

[Parent, FG2, P19]

“So I kind of learnt a little bit about some of the spices and learning that you don’t always need to have, it’s my backyard, it’s not a garden, it’s a backyard, it’s all slab!”

[Parent, FG3, P24]

This theme also revealed that the programme's environment fostered participation without judgement, and harboured a unique *inclusive and supportive environment* underpinning the personal empowerment and achievements. Similarly, there was a strong sentiment among parents of *feeling able to connect with others* from different ethnicities and backgrounds who had children at the same school. This was seen as a unique opportunity to get to know one another and after workshops, recognise and converse with them:

"We're good. We all got on. Yeah, we spoke to people that we'd never speak to. Do you know what I mean?"

[Parent, FG2, P19]

"But now I can recognise them, you know, all ladies who are in the kitchen."

[Parent, FG3, P27]

Pride and enthusiasm of contribution

This theme reflects the parental involvement within the positive social environment and the opportunities the programme had created to explore their passion for food and embrace cultural traditions together. Parents explained their passion for healthy food and that their ability to contribute to the workshops had built plenty of *enthusiasm for their contribution* to programme as the weeks passed by. Parents also valued the chance to teach, cook, and learn together with descriptions indicating how invaluable this experience was. *Cultural pride in sharing* was clear as they exchanged recipes and discussed the methods used and prepare food together the cooking workshops in keeping with their heritage or traditions:

"it was more to show myself and meet other people, another culture, another cuisine, because I was doing cooking as well. And I love to share my tradition, my recipe, my meal."

[Parent, FG2, P15]

Complementing this, *enjoyment was founded on a shared passion* as parents managed to connect socially, build positive relationships in the workshops because of their mutual interest in food, cooking and growing:

"They loved it, they loved it to watch it grow and go back a couple of weeks later to see it all, didn't they? They did, they liked it. We did enjoy it."

[Parent, FG2, P19]

"And I did my Polish soup and I did pakora and I love it, you know. And I'm doing often these dishes, so I love to learn more. I am so happy to know more."

[Parent, FG2, P15]

Experiential learning opportunity

This theme recognises the importance of the interactive and immersive learning environment both parents and their children were introduced to via the experiences of growing, cooking, tasting, and exploring food together. Experiences nurtured curiosity and a strong sense of *food connectedness* was evident in the focus group conversations. Through engaging in the practical growing and cooking workshops the programme provided, parents and their children were exposed to the *hands-on and sensory learning* environment which helped establish growing, cooking or culinary practices:

"We picked them. We planted them"

[Parent, FG2, P19]

"...(talking about washing radishes) Kitchen Spinners, then they washed it, they spin it to take water off and they could eat straight away."

[Parent, FG3, P22]

Parents noted that their children’s participation in the programme led to a greater *willingness to try new foods* (particularly vegetables), highlighting the potential for the programme’s components to embed learning beyond the school environment and extend into the home:

“Before children is not eating like a vegetable, after this session, children like a vegetable and Spanish carrots.”

[Parent, FG3, P28]

“The spinach one, yeah, my children, they start enjoying spinach at home since that time, yeah.”

[Parent, FG3, P22]

4.3. Motivations for Attendance and Community Contribution

Focus group discussions suggested that attendance was shaped by several interconnected factors. Building relationships and developing connections emerged as an important motivator. Parents cited individual aspirations, such as the advantages of acquiring practical knowledge and skills and the potential to enhance family wellbeing also played a significant role in engagement with the programme. In the cooking workshops, parents were able to shape their tutoring role, fostering a sense of contribution and recognition by sharing their skills, knowledge, ideas and cultural cuisine to others. Furthermore, there was a strong sentiment of equitably participation that ensured that parents and children from varied cultural backgrounds could engage meaningfully.

Social connection

This theme reflects the strong opinion that the programme led to significant social bonding, relationship building, and it was useful for those parents who were seeking opportunities to interact and strengthen community networks from different cultures. Parents frequently outlined how they had *developed connections through meeting new*

people, because of the workshop locality, inclusivity and interactive elements which allowed for conversation and 'getting to know' opportunities during session at the school sites:

"So after this, you know, the cooking session, before I don't know who they are. But now I can recognise them, you know, all ladies who are in the kitchen"

[Parent, FG3, P27]

"I'm very...backwards for making friends and these things...Yes, but once I start here doing the cooking class before with XXXXX and they also joined. I have friends now. I can say"

[Parent, FG2, P12]

After attending the workshops, becoming familiar with each other and progressing with the skills sharing, parents experienced a *feeling of belonging and achievement together* while they participated in the workshops. Additionally, parents were able to openly share and exchange food-related practices alongside traditional values as the cooking workshops supplied a regular and purposeful *cultural and community sharing* opportunity:

"...so I was looking forward to that we'll have different dishes. And we did have that in the end. So it was our cooking, Egyptian, Polish...So we had a few dishes that we were bringing in and sharing with each other. That was nice."

[Parent, FG2, P13]

"I think food overall just brings everyone together...errrm... So I think that food was really good. I think that it just brings anyone and everyone together"

[Parent, FG2, P11]

Personal Drivers

This theme reflects the perceived benefits but also the personal intrigue of the parents who attended the programme's workshops. The focus groups revealed considerable *curiosity, interest or benefit in learning about cooking/food/growing* with parents frequently citing new knowledge and the practical skills they learned were useful:

"Outside of this group, I don't think I would have tried Polish dumplings, and we tried the potato dumplings."

[Parent, FG2, P13]

"We've learned a lot. I mean, especially when look...there's some ingredients that you look: but you never find. And then with different cultural backgrounds."

[Parent, FG2, P11]

Additionally, the parents recognised the chance to improve their health and their families. After a series of workshops with their children involved, the *children wanted parents to attend (and vice versa)* more often, which reflects a valued mutual motivational relationship while attending together:

"I wanted to tell you that just that it's I think so it's not just for us as adult citizen, I do this cooking classes make us happy."

[Parent, FG2, P12]

"My oldest daughter has come to me when I go to the kitchen and the cooking. And she is standing with me."

[Parent, FG2, P17]

Because of their participation in regular workshops, and the connections made, both parents and stakeholders felt that the experience on the programme provided an authentic *opportunity to practice and improve English language skills*:

"For me, it's really helpful, the courses like this, because I can engage with people, you know"

[Parent, FG2, P13]

Influencing personal positioning

This theme reflects how the programme raised individual profiles and aspirations among parents. After becoming recognised in the group, several parents had been actively involved in influencing and inspiring the wider community with their cultural dishes. The cooking workshops provided opportunities for parents to tutor, facilitate and actively contribute to the *learning techniques and skill sharing* to the rest of the group, which was necessary to make their cultural dishes:

"I'll probably cook curry, and then someone else will cook curry...And then you just watch their techniques and their cooking skills and stuff like that. So you do learn. You do learn a lot."

[Parent, FG2, P11]

Parents involved in the cooking workshops described *presenting traditional cuisine* as both an enjoyable and meaningful experience. For many, it was a moment of pride and, at times, an emotive and seen as an opportunity to inspire other parents to take action. Additionally, some parents expressed interest in exploring business opportunities, considering ways to build on their experience and were thinking of *progression to further opportunities* including influencing the school food menu served to children at lunchtimes:

"It was the school's take on her recipe and they took her...So they took her recipe... "

[Parent, FG2, P13]

"my favourite is cooking. And I love to cooking...And I try to open my own business; It's like restaurant."

[Parent, FG2, P17]

Inclusivity creating involvement

This theme highlights the programme's fair access for all those that attended the workshops, but also the delivery style enabled the contribution of parents to be at the forefront of the learning and to think about what they might do next, together. The *opportunity to understand others and their way of life*, including diverse perspectives, different dishes, growing experiences and food preparation techniques interested and inspired parents but also stakeholders:

"For me, I think it's coming, like bringing people together... more closer community together, people together....do something together. This is what I wish for us to do more...not be like alienated in this community"

[Parent, FG2, P15]

"I think we have to recognise, not underestimate, how good the people were, particularly those who were sharing their cooking expertise and that is something that's missing in a lot of British homes."

[Stakeholder, FG1, P8]

Accompanying this, parents felt that being able to contribute to the workshops, with their experiences and traditions activity encouraged led to a strong *sentiment of collective learning and action* and the parents intimated sustaining future contact and socialisation by *preparing to evolve group* outside of the programme:

“Yes, I think we still have a lot to share”

[Parent, FG2, P15]

“So maybe have like an after-school club. Maybe you come in after school club and that's probably second one.”

[Parent, FG2, P11]

4.4. Impact on Food Provision, Education and the Learning Environment

The focus groups provide the platform for both stakeholders and parents to discuss the impact of the programme. It was felt that the school had become an invaluable setting because of the ability to bring people together, create social connections and react and adapt to the requests, changes and suggestions. Stakeholders felt that this flexible and inclusive learning environment served to address gaps in knowledge and embed practical food skills beyond the classroom extending the learning beyond the classroom.

School as a community hub around food

This theme represents the integration of cultural traditions and culinary experiences into the school environment creating an engaging ‘hub’ which firmly promoted *understanding and mutual respect for food* as well as aiming to *develop relationships and confidence* in cooking and growing for the parents involved:

“Just the emphasis on the food itself, and having that entry point and bringing people in, with no judgement, and starting from a very basic level of working.”

[Stakeholder, FG1, P9]

“So we need to have a low stakes entry point where nobody feels judged or anything like that. These ladies that I watched that room. They were like...This is...yeah...this is me! I'm going to show you how to do this.”

[Stakeholder, FG1, P8]

Additionally, the experience of delivering this programme did *extend, adapt and improve the learning space* on offer at the local schools to allow the parents and children to be part of a connected food-related experience.

“Then you put that into a real-life context, they've grown, from scratch, the ingredients,

then they come to harvest them, then they make their own smoothies. There was not one child who refused to taste them.”

[Stakeholder, FG1, P2]

Recognition of the food learning journey

This theme recognised the programme’s contribution to the full learning and application journey. Stakeholders noted that attendees had increased aptitude for growing and had built awareness around food sources as well as their ability to use ingredients at home suggesting an exciting *gardener to cook, cook to role model* relationship developing. Similarly, the programme’s range of activities, from growing ingredients to preparing and sharing a variety of dishes, embodied the *seed to plate journey*, symbolising a holistic approach to food education and parental empowerment:

“The project made me feel like it mattered, because there was real people involved, they got a say and then there's a product they could point to and say I did that.”

[Stakeholder, FG1, P8]

“they learn how to chop, they learn the skills, they stir, they do all those things, they design and they taste.”

[Stakeholder, FG1, P2]

Accompanying this, there was further recognition about the sense of *putting food first* in-terms of the planning the cooking workshops and allowing for a flexible approach to what was delivered:

“It's just stripping everything back and you focus on the food rather than actual cookery lesson, and the tactileness and bringing people in actually using the ingredients and not focussing on the end result.”

[Stakeholder, FG1, P9]

5. Limitations

It is important to recognise that this research project was designed to provide a detailed account of key stakeholders' perceptions of the FfT programme. The findings reflect perceptions rather than objective data. Additionally, the research focused on selected stakeholder and parental views and does not include the experiences of children who did have contact and involvement in the programme. While this may appear to be a limitation, the research specifically sought input from stakeholders and parents who had been involved regularly and/or observed all aspects of the programme. This allowed these contributors to offer a critical appraisal of the programme by responding to all questions at a satisfactory level in the focus groups. In contrast, feedback from children could be considered but the level of depth and insight of the programme in response to the research agenda at primary school age is questionable.

Although the number of participants in this research project may seem relatively small in terms of programme's reach, the aim was not to achieve large numbers but to ensure representation of the intended participant groups. In this respect, the sample included a substantial proportion of FfT programme stakeholders, and the parents involved in programme who understood and witnessed the realities of implementation. The inclusion of school catering team at each school and their perspectives was an omission in this piece of work. Perspectives from these stakeholders would have been welcomed to consider the feasibility and acceptability of preparing the creative parental dishes and / or using the ingredients grown in the school menu. While the thematic findings acknowledge this area (see 'Influencing personal positioning' - page 12), the research questions and subsequent analysis in this study was not sufficiently developed to offer a full and detailed account of the contribution and impact on the catering service. This would be a worthy extension of the research work, as well as the focus on influencing school food and monitoring free school meal uptake over a prolonged period.

6. Research Recommendations

This research project gathered feedback on the integration of the FFT programme in school settings from both stakeholders and parents. They had overwhelming positive comments and were supportive of this programme in the local area. The following recommendations are informed by these findings which explored i) Programme planning, delivery and receipt; ii) Motivations for attendance and Contribution, and; iii) Food provision, education and the environment for learning:

- Embed culturally inclusive workshops as a core element of future programmes:

The findings suggest that the high levels satisfaction and sustained parental engagement in this programme was because of the:

- i) Open and inclusive environment which supported the social connections made between parents, and;
- ii) The flexible and accommodating workshop delivery style and content of workshops that allowed for multi-cultural input *by* the parents.

- Maintain opportunities for parents to lead or co-facilitate programme activities:

The findings suggest that the programme's intergenerational and participant-centred approach and parental enthusiasm reinforced cultural pride. Parents felt valued and their contributions to teaching and informing others in their community was integral to their positive experience.

- Influence School food provision:

The findings suggested the parents had managed to influence provision of food at school and for those in the community. With some development, the programme could establish stronger relationships between the school (including catering teams) and the community to include further recipe ideas or dishes from the parent-led cooking sessions and / or the growing of food items to be used in the school meals.

- Improve the clarity of what is expected from participants:

The findings suggested there was a requirement for clear and accessible pre-information before the programme commenced. Specifically, information on the involvement of children and the type of cooking activities involved in the cooking workshops may have been explained with more precision.

- Achieve consistency with communication and provision:

The findings suggested that there were challenges in achieving consistency of messages to parents regarding their participation and what they were asked to do. Additionally, provision of food for the cooking workshops was also noted to be a problematic at times and several parents highlighting missing ingredients and a reliance on them bringing items in.

- Explore the influence on school meals and free school meals as the programme expands:

The findings of this report cannot be directly linked to changes in school meal uptake, whether free or paid. In light of parental involvement in changing elements of school meal menu on offer to children in this report, consideration should be made on to linking data to information on school meal uptake within the local authority and the FFT programme should this continue to expand.

7. Summary and Conclusion

The Food for Thought (FfT) programme in Doncaster was designed as a bold, 'test and learn' initiative, aiming to strengthen community engagement through growing and cooking food activities in primary school settings. This research used a qualitative methodology to draw upon the valuable insights from stakeholders and parents via three focus groups, which explored: i) Programme planning, delivery and receipt, ii) Motivations for attendance and Contribution, and iii) Food provision, education and the environment for learning.

Data indicated that the FfT programme demonstrated strong potential as an innovative, locally embedded approach for food education and social inclusion. While challenges in planning and delivery required attention, the overwhelmingly positive feedback, enjoyable and aspirational workshop content and clear demand for continuation emphasised the value of the programme. From the perspectives of participants, this programme can evolve into a sustainable initiative that enhances social connection, wellbeing, cultural exchange, and food education outcomes across Doncaster. Encouragingly, other schools in the local area have expressed interest in accommodating the programme, and further growing workshops are planned across three primary schools in early 2026.

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9. Appendices

Appendix A. Recipe booklet resource created by parents

A resource created by the parents involved in the cooking workshops is available to view here: [Click here: Online Flipbook](#) and is available from: <https://heyzine.com/flip-book/b08e7c7ad0.html>

Appendix B. Food for Thought workshop descriptions

Cooking workshops: The sessions are designed to empower attendees, by encouraging an exchange of knowledge in 'teach ins' and 'skill swaps' so parents can showcase their cultural knowledge and provide relevant examples of culinary practices. Alongside the series of workshops, the parents are creating a 'community cookbook' illustrating the recipes that they are produced by the workshop group.

Growing workshops: Gro-box were commissioned to provide a series of Eco Garden Garden workshops at each School site. The workshops include the design and provision of growing space at each school using self-watering raised beds. The intention is for attendees to take their learning home and be able to grow their own produce, creating a sustainable healthy growing environment at home. The *Gro-box Ltd* team interact with attendees of the workshop, sharing ideas on sowing and growing and can provide advice for those parents intending to grow vegetables that are not traditional to England.

Core learning agenda:

Interactive Sessions:

- 'Teach-ins' are structured as interactive sessions where community members can learn about specific topics related to food, culture, and sustainability.
- These sessions are led by "unconventional educators" who have expertise in various areas.

Diverse Topics:

- Topics can range from cooking techniques and cultural cuisine to food science, ecology, and sustainable practices.
- Each session focuses on practical knowledge and skills that participants can apply in their daily lives.

Community Involvement:

- Teach-ins encourage active participation and discussion among attendees.
- They provide a platform for sharing experiences, asking questions, and engaging in hands-on activities.

Exchange of Expertise:

- Skills swaps involve community members exchanging their skills and knowledge with each other.
- Participants take turns teaching and learning different skills, fostering a collaborative learning environment.

Practical Demonstrations:

- These sessions include practical 'show and tell' moments.
- For example, someone might demonstrate how to prepare a traditional dish from their culture, while others learn and try it themselves.

Building Connections:

- Skills swaps help build connections between community members by highlighting the diverse talents and knowledge within the community.
- They promote mutual respect and appreciation for different cultures and skills.

Both 'teach-ins' and 'skills swaps' emphasize hands-on learning, allowing participants to actively engage and practice new skills. These activities provide opportunities for cultural exchange, helping participants learn about and appreciate different traditions and practices. By sharing knowledge and skills, community members empower each other and strengthen the community.

Appendix C. Research Participant Characteristics: Parents

Age

Age Group	Count	% of Total
25-34	1	5
35-44	12	63
45-54	3	16
55-64	2	11
Not Stated	1	5
Total	19	100%

Gender

Gender	Count	% of Total
Female	18	95
Male	1	5
Total	19	100%

Ethnicity

Ethnicity	Count	% of Total
White	10	53
Asian	5	26
Other: Kurdish	1	5
Other: White Romanian	1	5
Other: White African	1	5
Other: Not stated	1	5
Total	19	100%

Education

Level	Count	% of Total
GCSEs / O Levels / Equivalent	5	26
A Levels / Vocational Qualification	3	16
Undergraduate degree	3	16
No formal education	2	11
Level 2 English	1	5
Other	4	21
Not Stated	1	5
Total	19	100%

Employment Status

Status	Count	% of Total
Employed part-time	8	42
Unemployed	5	26
Self-employed	2	11
Student	1	5
Employed full-time	1	5
Not stated	1	5
Other	1	5
Total	19	100%

Household Income

Income Band	Count	% of Total
Less than £10000	2	11
£10000-19999	4	21
£20000-29999	2	11
£30000-39999	1	5
£40000-49999	1	5
Not stated	3	16
Prefer not to say	6	32
Total	19	100%

Postcode

Area	Count	% of Total
DN4	7	37
DN1	4	21
DN2	1	5
Not Stated	7	37
Total	19	100%

Long-term Health Condition or Disability

Condition Status	Count	% of Total
Yes	2	11
No	12	63
Prefer not to say	1	5
Not stated	4	21
Total	19	100%

Appendix D. Research Participant Characteristics: Stakeholders

Age

Age Group	Count	% of Total
25-34	1	11
35-44	3	33
45-54	3	33
55-64	2	23
Total	19	100%

Gender

Gender	Count	% of Total
Female	7	78
Male	2	12
Total	9	100%

Ethnicity

Ethnicity	Count	% of Total
White	9	100%
Total	9	100%

Appendix E. Focus Group Topic and Questioning Guide

Main Question Topic A - General Views:

Programme participant Q. What did you think about the food for thought programme?

Example Prompts:

- *Enjoyment? Disappointment?*
- *Benefits / negatives to participation or provision?*
- *Did the programme meet expectations? / What was expected?*

Other Stakeholder Q. What did you think about the food for thought programme?

Example prompts:

- *Enjoyment / disappointment aspects from taking part?*
- *Achievement / positive experiences?*
- *Negative experiences?*

Main Question B - Current Programme Receipt:

Programme participant Q. What can you now do, after having the Food for Thought programme at your school?

Example Prompts:

- *Ability to cook, hygiene, prepare – intervention specific*
- *Inform and help parents / siblings or teachers at home*
- *Generated new skills / ideas and interest / confidence*
- *Able service provider to benefit service users*
- *Effect on children and their learning / participation – impact on health*
- *Opportunity to learning / enjoy new skills - intervention specific*

Other Stakeholder Q. What outcomes were achieved by the children / young people in the workshops?

Example prompts:

- *Better understand on how to cater for different community groups (intergenerational aspect)*
- *Parental engagement and confidence in supporting their children*
- *Knowledge, skills and behaviours did the learners achieve*

Main Question C - Programme Delivery and Interaction:

Programme participant Q. How did you find the Food for Thought workshops and Classes?

Example Prompts:

- *Fun, enjoyable, able to learn*
- *Comments regarding the Food for Thought specifically to the workshops*
- *Unhappy and disinterested*
- *Did students engage with anything that was delivered?*
- *Enhancement of the education material / learning environment*
- *Judgement of what constitutes really beneficial / influential and explore participant reasons*

Other Stakeholder Q. How did you feel the participants responded to the workshops in the Food for Thought programme?

Example Prompts (stakeholders):

- *How did learners engage and interact within the workshops*
- *Changed how you will deliver activity in the future*
- *General feelings of the attendees disinterested (or wanting to know more)?*
- *How do the reactions of the participants in workshop make you feel*

Main Question D - Influence on learning environment and community:

Programme participant Q. Did the programme help you to connect with other people in the community? - How so?

Example Prompts:

- *Were you welcomed and felt a sense of value?*
- *Has the programme contributed to the local community (beyond the school wall!)*
- *Do you feel you've made a real contribution?*
- *Have you any really good examples of working together?*
- *Has the provision and environment changed at the school for the better?*

Other Stakeholder Q. Has the programme been influential in your relationship with the school(s)?

Example prompts:

- *Did everyone take part positively?*
- *More engaged in school activities since taking part in the programme?*
- *Further thoughts on connecting the community with the school environment as a result from taking part in this programme.*
- *Has this work inspired new initiatives?*

Main Question E - Overall opinions of the programme:

Participant and other Stakeholder Q. What are your overall opinions on the Food for Thought programme?

Example Prompts:

- *The positives / overall benefits*
- *The negatives*
- *Issues to work on for improvement: What will you do differently as a result of delivering this programme?*
- *If anything, what could be done better – or suggestions for progression?*
- *Challenges overcome?*

**FG facilitator provides and summary of the discussion and presents an opportunity for anything else that was possibly missed.*

Appendix F. Overall thematic findings from the analysis

